

Working Group on Reforming Academic Career Assessment

Case study “Declaration of principles: A new research assessment towards a socially relevant science in Latin America and the Caribbean”

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Country	Country/Region/International Latin America and the Caribbean
Name	Official name of the initiative Declaration of principles: A new research assessment towards a socially relevant science in Latin America and the Caribbean
Institution	Name of the institution(s) responsible for the initiative Latin American Council of Social Sciences (CLACSO)- Latin American Forum for Research Assessment (FOLEC)
Stakeholders	Names of other organisations/communities involved <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AmeliCA Conocimiento Abierto • LATINDEX • Redalyc • IDRC • AGORRA Observatory, UKRI <p>In particular, the declaration has more than 300 adherents.</p>
Year	When the initiative was launched 2022
Documentation	Link to the main document describing the initiative <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Una nueva evaluación académica y científica para una ciencia con relevancia social en América Latina y el Caribe <p>A new research assessment towards a socially relevant science in Latin America and the Caribbean</p>
Website	Link to the website of the initiative (if available)

	https://www.clacso.org/a-new-research-asesment-towards-a-socially-relevant-science-in-latin-america-and-the-caribbean/
Summary	<p>Brief description of the initiative</p> <p>This declaration was approved by the XXVII General Assembly of CLACSO, in the framework of the <u>9th Latin American and Caribbean Conference of Social Sciences</u>, in Mexico City in June 2022. In turn, it was enriched by the contributions of various regional and international specialists and representatives of CLACSO member centres, who participated in the plenary «Balance, perspectives and challenges for a new agenda for research assessment in Latin America and the Caribbean» at the International Seminar of the Latin American Forum for Scientific Assessment (FOLEC)- CLACSO during the 9th. Conference.</p> <p>In this way, CLACSO-FOLEC, together with a multiplicity of actors committed to the issue, has managed to consolidate a common and highly consensual Declaration of Principles on responsible research assessment from and for Latin America and the Caribbean. It is made up of 14 principles, which are organized in three dimensions: On the aims of assessment, On the assessment processes, On the information systems and indicators.</p> <p>Following these guidelines, CLACSO-FOLEC seeks to promote the implementation of these principles – turned into proposals and tools for action – by National Science and Technology Organisations, scientific institutions and higher education institutions in the region. It also encourages the study and survey of good practices and different innovations in the assessment processes, which improve the quality of research in close connection with the needs of our societies and the diverse and democratic representation of their populations, as well as prioritizing and expanding openness, collaboration and participation in the production and circulation of knowledge.</p>
Target audience	<p>Description of the main target audience of the initiative</p> <p>National Science and Technology Agencies, scientific and higher education institutions, researchers, research funding agencies, public policy makers, librarians, academic and university publishers.</p>
Geographical Scope	<p>Description of the primary geographical scope of application</p> <p>Latin America and the Caribbean</p>

<p>International potential:</p>	<p>Description of the international potential for adaptation</p> <p>CLACSO-FOLEC Declaration of Principles contributes to international conversation on responsible research assessment reform with a concerted and inclusive initiative, which is context-sensitive, cognizant of different challenges faced by Social Sciences and Humanities in different parts of the world and that enrich heterogeneity of research assessment ecosystem, while at the same time ensures sufficient homogeneity among some common principles o enable a genuinely global reform.</p>
<p>Goal</p>	<p>Description of the intended change</p> <p>The declaration seeks to promote the implementation of the 14 principles - turned into proposals and tools for action - by National Science and Technology Agencies, scientific institutions and higher education institutions in the region. It also encourages the study and survey of good practices and different innovations in evaluation processes that improve the quality of research in close connection with the needs of societies and the diverse and democratic representation of their populations, as well as prioritizing and expanding openness, collaboration and participation in the production and circulation of knowledge.</p>
<p>Relevance</p>	<p>Description of the key elements that are relevant for reforming career assessment</p> <p>Regarding reforms in the assessment of research careers, the declaration asserts that it is essential for the academic community to regain participation over evaluation processes and indicators, and to review evaluation policies based on incentives for publication with an impact factor, as they affect the local autonomy of agendas while discouraging good open access practices and the social interaction of scientific research (principle 4).</p> <p>In addition, it addresses assessment processes as “evolutionary, self-reflective, transparent, and participatory, promoting mechanisms that encourage dialogue and mutual learning, and ensure continuous improvement, not only for the scientific community but also for citizens, including social and community referents in its development” (principle 9).</p> <p>On the other hand, it states that it is necessary to guarantee the representation of women and diversities in evaluation systems and processes, in a minimum of parity and in research priorities and their themes; likewise, it is also desirable to advance towards a universal</p>

	<p>system of citations and bibliographic references with a gender perspective, which makes visible and prioritizes the production of women in academic and scientific fields (principle 11).</p> <p>Finally, it considers peer review as part of the researcher's activities and as a relevant contribution to the scientific and academic community, promoting and rewarding the highest quality and integrity in its development (principle 10).</p>
Qualitative	<p>Description of recommendations regarding qualitative assessment</p> <p>Principle 2. Adaptation to the current stage of open science is needed, through new assessment policies that give priority to the qualitative assessment of research, respecting national states autonomy to determine their own assessment criteria, according to their specific contexts, contemplating different research profiles, various alternatives and instruments of intervention both in terms of funding policies and in the accreditation of institutions, and in the field of practices that involve the people who evaluate and are evaluated in their teaching, research, extension and/or linking activities, among others.</p>
Quantitative	<p>Description of recommendations regarding quantitative assessment</p> <p>Principle 13. Information systems at science and technology public agencies and research funding institutions should reflect the career of researchers and teachers doing extension, linking and social intervention along with those who are training, as well as the complete scientific production of each university and country, respecting the diversity of institutional and disciplinary cultures and their diverse means of communication.</p> <p>Principle 14. The citation indicators extracted from the databases limited in their geographical, linguistic and disciplinary scope should not be considered a valid measure to carry out comparison of scientific production between individuals, institutions or countries. It is necessary to promote the creation and the use of databases which reflect both the production disseminated in international repositories as well as that which is included in regional and local databases.</p>
Diversity	<p>Description of how initiative recognizes and supports consideration of diversity contributions, outputs and impacts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognition and rewards of different missions: research, teaching, extension, outreach and social intervention activities. • Incentives for Multilingualism.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social impact and relevance, with specific definitions for the social sciences, humanities and arts. • In collaborative processes, it is essential to consider the contribution of non-academic actors, as well as Afro communities and other historically excluded groups in order to avoid cognitive extractivism.
Intersectoral	<p>Description of how initiative recognizes and supports consideration of intersectorality</p> <p>Implicit in the different dimensions included in the Statement.</p>
Career-stage	<p>Description of how initiative recognizes and supports consideration of career-stage</p> <p>Principle 12. Attention should be paid in the early stages of academic and research careers to the problems of inclusion that originate in inadequate assessment practices, as well as to provide support to those who are starting out so that they can incorporate good evaluative practices and become potential agents of change.</p>
Career-path	<p>Description of how initiative recognizes and supports consideration of career-paths</p> <p>Principle 2. Adaptation to the current stage of open science is needed, through new assessment policies that give priority to the qualitative assessment of research, respecting national states autonomy to determine their own assessment criteria, according to their specific contexts, contemplating different research profiles, various alternatives and instruments of intervention both in terms of funding policies and in the accreditation of institutions, and in the field of practices that involve the people who evaluate and are evaluated in their teaching, research, extension and/or linking activities, among others.</p>
Toolbox	<p>Description of related practical guides and toolkits</p> <p>2. Una nueva evaluación académica y científica para una ciencia con relevancia social en América Latina y el Caribe</p> <p>A new research assessment towards a socially relevant science in Latin America and the Caribbean</p>

<p>Implementation</p>	<p>Description of implementation process</p> <p>Organizational signers of CLACSO-FOLEC’s Declaration of Principles are part of a learning community with aspirations to improve research and researcher assessment, that are at different stages of institutional change for research assessment reform. Through diverse mobilization actions, co-producing and sharing tools for designing responsible assessment policies and participating in different research on research projects, CLACSO-FOLEC seeks to incentivize implementation processes.</p>
<p>Uptake</p>	<p>Description of implementation uptake</p> <p>Same as last point.</p>
<p>Challenges</p>	<p>Description of identified implementation challenges/obstacles.</p> <p>A first challenge for higher education institutions and science and technology bodies is to recognise the exclusionary and limited practices of current evaluation systems for assessing scientific activity, both in the primary assessment of the impact factor and also in relation to other knowledge systems, language, social impact, representation of women and diversity in all disciplines.</p> <p>A second challenge is the necessity to work in the construction of regional indicators based on open scientific information that are left aside the “mainstream” databases, namely output in Spanish, Portuguese and indigenous languages published in Open Access in journals indexed in Latin American services. One of the main obstacles is the lack of a regional platform to collect the different journal platforms, portals and repositories, which is a key issue in order to advance in more diverse and responsible research assessment.</p>
<p>Benefits</p>	<p>Description of identified implementation benefits.</p> <p>Bottom-up sensibilization around “responsible research assessment” among working groups across partner institutions and organizations. Working groups participate in institutional training initiatives, drive internal change within CLACSO’s network, and generate policy briefs for regional research assessment-related issues. Stakeholders involved in these processes include academic leadership, researchers, institution library staff, research management staff, and governmental policy staff. Given the broad scope of countries in Latin America and the Caribbean that FOLEC encompasses, local participation and contextualization is essential to facilitate relevant and effective reform. Top- down gradual but growing involvement</p>

	from regional science and technology organizations, universities and research centers.
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